

Stakeholder Engagement and Land Conflict Resolution in Arid and Semi-Arid Counties in Kenya

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Abstract:

The study aimed to examine the relationship between stakeholder engagement and land conflict resolution in Kenya's Arid and Semi-Arid Lands (ASAL) counties. It was grounded in the Collaborative Governance Theory. The target population consisted of 803 individuals from 23 ASAL counties, including 115 land department officials (5 per county), 113 sub-county administrators, and 575 ward administrators. The researcher employed descriptive and correlational research designs, with a sample size of 267 respondents, determined using Slovin's formula. Qualitative data were analyzed through content analysis, while quantitative data were analyzed using

both descriptive and inferential statistics. The rejection of the null hypotheses highlighted the importance of stakeholder participation, capacity building, and information transparency in resolving land conflicts. Key recommendations include enhancing coordination among administrative bodies and establishing multi-stakeholder platforms for more effective conflict resolution.

Keywords: *Land Conflict Resolution, Governance, Stakeholder Engagement, Semi-arid and Arid Counties.*

Introduction

Arid and semi-arid lands are crucial for biodiversity conservation, food security, and the livelihoods of millions of people, particularly in regions where they are the primary source of water, grazing, and agricultural resources [(United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP),2021)]. Land conflicts in arid and semi-arid regions are primarily driven by the scarcity of resources, such as water and fertile land, which are critical for the livelihoods of local populations. These regions often support pastoralist and agro-pastoralist communities whose survival depends on access to grazing

lands and water sources. Climate variability and prolonged droughts exacerbate resource scarcity, intensifying competition among different user groups. This competition frequently leads to conflicts between pastoralists and farmers, as well as among pastoralist communities themselves over grazing areas and water points. Additionally, the lack of clear land tenure systems and inadequate legal frameworks further complicate the situation, making it difficult to resolve disputes amicably (Haro, Doyo, & McPeak, 2020; Omollo, 2021).

Governance mechanisms are vital in resolving land conflicts by providing structured,

transparent, and equitable processes for managing disputes. They encompass legal frameworks that establish clear land ownership and usage laws, institutional arrangements like land courts and commissions for specialized dispute resolution, and participatory processes that engage stakeholders in decision-making (Alden-Wily, 2020). Additionally, these mechanisms ensure transparency and accountability, build capacity among local authorities and communities, and implement proactive measures such as land use planning to prevent conflicts (Deininger & Savastano, 2021). Together, these elements create a stable environment where land issues can be resolved fairly and efficiently, fostering social stability and sustainable development (Holden, Otsuka, & Deininger, 2022).

Collaborative Governance approach, in this study conceptualized as stakeholder engagement, emphasizes the involvement of multiple stakeholders in the decision-making process. Governance mechanisms here include formal and informal resolution methods, government and user-based procedures, arbitration, and mediation, all aimed at fostering better management solutions through knowledge integration from diverse sources (scientific and non-scientific) (Gash, 2022). The Polycentric Governance model, conceptualized as authority distribution, is characterized by multiple overlapping authorities at different levels, which can effectively manage complex issues like land conflicts. Polycentric governance promotes cooperation among various centers of decision-making, enhancing flexibility and adaptability in conflict resolution (Thiel, 2017). Institutional Analysis and Development (IAD) Framework, conceptualized as institutional framework in the current study, was developed by Ostrom (2019), the IAD framework focuses on the rules, norms, and strategies that shape interactions among individuals and groups within institutions. This framework is crucial for understanding how governance structures can be designed to manage and resolve land conflicts efficiently (McGinnis, 2019).

Saudi Arabia's ASALs, including parts of the Nefud Desert and the Rub' al Khali, face land

conflicts arising from rapid urbanization, agricultural expansion, and traditional land use practices. Governance mechanisms such as the National Land Use Planning Initiative and the Land Dispute Resolution Commission aim to address these conflicts by promoting sustainable land management practices and resolving disputes through legal frameworks and mediation processes (World Bank, 2018). Moreover, community-based land tenure systems and tribal councils play important roles in resolving conflicts and managing land resources in rural areas (Al-Khalaf, 2019).

Egypt's ASALs face land conflicts arising from factors such as land tenure insecurity, competing land uses, and water scarcity. Governance mechanisms such as the Land Use Planning Law and the Desert Development Strategy aim to address these conflicts by regulating land use practices, promoting sustainable resource management, and encouraging investments in desert areas (Ministry of Housing, Utilities, and Urban Communities, 2018). Additionally, community-based initiatives, supported by local government institutions and international organizations, empower local communities to manage their lands sustainably and resolve conflicts through participatory decision-making and dialogue (UNDP, 2020). These mechanisms, facilitated by tribal leaders and local councils, complement formal legal processes and help resolve conflicts in a culturally sensitive manner (Abdel-Meguid, 2016). By promoting inclusive governance structures, clarifying land tenure rights, and fostering dialogue between stakeholders, these mechanisms contribute to social stability and sustainable development in Egypt's arid and semi-arid regions.

The government of Kenya has implemented various governance mechanisms, including the establishment of community conservancies and the National Land Commission, to address land conflicts and promote sustainable land management. Additionally, Kenya has adopted participatory land-use planning processes and community land registration initiatives to secure land tenure rights and enhance local governance in ASALs. Traditional conflict resolution mechanisms, deeply rooted in local customs and

traditions, also play a significant role in resolving land disputes and promoting social cohesion in Kenya's ASALs. These mechanisms, facilitated by local elders, clan leaders, and community councils, complement formal legal processes and help resolve conflicts in a culturally sensitive manner (Mwangi, 2018). By promoting inclusive governance structures, clarifying land tenure rights, and fostering dialogue between stakeholders, these mechanisms contribute to social stability and sustainable development in Kenya's arid and semi-arid regions.

Statement of the Problem

Arid and semi-arid counties in Kenya face persistent challenges related to land governance and conflict resolution, which threaten social stability, economic development, and environmental sustainability. Despite various governance mechanisms in place, land conflicts persist, adversely affecting communities and hindering progress in these regions (Transparency International, 2018). According to a study conducted by the National Land Commission (NLC), arid and semi-arid counties experience a disproportionately high frequency of land conflicts compared to other regions in Kenya (NLC, 2022). These conflicts often arise due to competing claims over land resources, including pastureland, water sources, and grazing areas (Ochilo & Ochong, 2021). In addition, land conflicts in arid and semi-arid counties have a significant impact on livelihoods, particularly for pastoralist communities. Statistics from the Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (KNBS) indicate that 78% of households in these regions rely on livestock farming as their primary source of income (KNBS, 2019). Land disputes disrupt traditional grazing patterns, leading to resource depletion, loss of livestock, and food insecurity (Wareng & Mohammed, 2023).

While many studies address the immediate causes and consequences of land conflicts and their subsequent resolution (Omokhoa & Okochukwu, 2018; Vanella & Ochoa, 2018), there is a conceptual gap regarding the underlying structural factors and root causes that perpetuate conflicts over land resources. Limited

attention has been paid to the role of governance mechanisms in land conflict resolution and particularly conceptual frameworks that integrate governance mechanisms such as stakeholder engagement, authority distribution, institutional frameworks and policy adaptation together with their underlying theories, that is; the Collaborative Governance Theory, Polycentric Governance Theory, Institutional Analysis and Development (IAD) Framework and Adaptive Governance Theory. The contextual scope of existing research on land conflicts is often limited to specific geographic locations or communities, overlooking broader regional and cross-border dynamics that influence conflict dynamics and governance mechanisms (Adam et al.2020; Denchie et al. 2021; John & Kabote, 2017; Heikilla, 2019; Omokhoa & Okochukwu, 2018; Vanella & Ochoa, 2018). Therefore, addressing these gaps in methodology, conceptual framework, and contextual gaps will enhance the depth and breadth of research on governance mechanisms and land conflict resolution in arid and semi-arid counties in Kenya, ultimately informing more evidence-based policy and practice in this critical area.

Objective of the Study

The objective of the study was to assess the relationship between stakeholder engagement and land conflict resolution in Arid and Semi-Arid Counties in Kenya.

Research Hypothesis

The study was premised on the following null hypothesis:

H₀₁: Stakeholder Engagement does not have a significant relationship with land conflict resolution in Arid and Semi-Arid Counties in Kenya.

Literature Review

The study was anchored on the Collaborative Governance Theory. The existing literature, "Collaborative governance" was first used by Dohahue of Harvard University in 2004 (Dohahue 2004) and was mentioned again in

2008 with Zeckhauser in Public Private Collaboration (Dohahue and Zeckhauser 2006). From the narrow sense, Ansell and Gash (2008) consider that one or more public agencies directly engage non-state stakeholders in a collective decision-making process that is formal, consensus-oriented, and deliberative, which aims to make or implement public policy or manage public programs or assets. The narrow concept emphasizes the public sector, and the decision-making process is usually formal. From the broad sense, Emerson and Nabatchi et al (2012) define collaborative governance broadly as the processes and structures of public policy decision making and management that engage people constructively across the boundaries of public agencies, levels of government, and/or the public, private and civic spheres in order to carry out a public purpose that could not otherwise be accomplished.

Collaborative governance theory emphasizes the involvement of multiple stakeholders in the decision-making process. Collaborative governance, as it has come to be known, brings public and private stakeholders together in collective forums with public agencies to engage in consensus-oriented decision making. This approach is grounded in the idea that inclusive participation enhances the legitimacy, acceptance, and effectiveness of governance decisions. In their study, Ansell and Gash (2008) identified a series of factors that are crucial within the collaborative process itself. These factors included face-to-face dialogue, trust building, and the development of commitment and shared understanding. The study found that a virtuous cycle of collaboration tends to develop when collaborative forums focus on “small wins” that deepen trust, commitment, and shared understanding. Collaborative governance theory has also attracted criticism among them being that decisions about the inclusion of representative stakeholders from organized segments of the community can come at the expense of less organized yet affected others. Many interests may not have an

organizational infrastructure that can represent them in a collaborative governance process (O’Brien, 2012).

The Key Concepts of the theory are relevant to governance in resource conflict resolution such as Stakeholder Engagement which is a mechanism for involving diverse stakeholders in collaborative governance processes. Stakeholder engagement involves inclusivity and information transparency which ensures that all relevant parties have access to information and decision-making. It also involves consensus and capacity building which seeks to foster agreement among stakeholders through dialogue and negotiation. In relation to the current study, this theory supports the idea that involving various stakeholders (IV: Stakeholder Engagement) in land conflict resolution leads to more effective and accepted outcomes (DV: Land Conflict Resolution).

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework explores the relationship between stakeholder engagement, as the independent variable, and land conflict resolution, as the dependent variable. Stakeholder engagement is defined by three key dimensions: stakeholder participation, information transparency, and capacity building. These elements are critical in shaping the conflict resolution process. Active participation of stakeholders ensures diverse perspectives are considered, while transparency in information sharing builds trust and accountability. Capacity building enhances the ability of stakeholders to contribute meaningfully to the process. In turn, land conflict resolution is evaluated through three outcomes: conflict reduction, satisfaction with the resolution process, effective implementation of resolutions, and equity in the outcomes. This framework suggests that robust stakeholder engagement can lead to a reduction in conflicts, greater satisfaction with the processes, successful implementation of resolutions, and more equitable outcomes for all parties involved.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive and correlational research designs. For this study on governance mechanisms for land conflict resolution in ASAL counties in Kenya, the target population was 803 individuals from the 23 ASAL Counties. The target population includes: Land Department Officials: 115 individuals (5 officials per county across 23 counties); Sub County Administrators: 113 individuals and Ward Administrators: 575 individuals. The sampling frame for this study was sourced from the department of County HR/Payroll 2023. The study used a sample of 267 respondents determined by Slovin’s sample size determination formulae. The study adopted purposive sampling for the (land department officials, sub-county administrators and ward administrators). Based on the groups representatives random sampling technique was adopted. This study collected both primary and secondary data. The pilot study was done to test validity and reliability of the research instruments. To attain content validity, the questionnaire measurement items were constructed from the conceptual frame work constructs to ensure that only items relating to the study variables are included in the tool. The quantitative data was analysed by the use of descriptive and inferential analysis.

Results

The stakeholder engagement was considered in terms of; stakeholder participation, information transparency and capacity building. Stakeholder engagement stands as a vital governance mechanism for land conflict resolution in Kenya's ASAL regions, fostering inclusivity and collaboration among diverse stakeholders for sustainable solutions. The Likert scale was employed to gauge respondents' perceptions of the statement, with options ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree), enabling participants to express their degree of agreement or disagreement with the statement. In order to guide analysis and interpretation purposes, a mean close to 1 indicates strong disagreement with the statement; a mean close to 3 suggests neutrality or ambivalence; and a mean close to 5 indicates strong agreement with the statement. Moreover, based on the standard deviations ranging from approximately 1.0 or lower may indicate a relatively high level of agreement or consensus among respondents (lower variability). Standard deviations exceeding 1.0 or higher suggest greater diversity or disagreement among respondents (higher variability).

Table 1. Stakeholder Engagement and Land Conflict Resolution

Statement	SA (%)	A (%)	N (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean	Std. Dev
Community members are frequently involved in land conflict resolution meetings	27.3	49.3	8	9.3	6	4.17	0.565
A diverse range of stakeholders participate in decision-making processes for land conflicts.	26.7	40	6.7	18.7	8	3.8	1.133
The decision-making process is inclusive of all relevant stakeholders.	37.3	18.7	26.7	15.3	2	3.88	1.073
Information regarding land conflict resolution processes is easily accessible	40.7	44	2.7	8	4.7	4.23	1.141
Updates on the progress of land conflict resolutions are provided regularly	19.3	38.7	13.3	24	4.7	3.87	1.169
The information shared during conflict resolution is transparent	15.3	43.3	19.3	20	2	3.9	1.026
Training programs for stakeholders involved in land conflict resolution are effective.	22	37.3	7.3	27.3	6	3.46	1.115
Capacity-building initiatives enhance stakeholders' participation in the resolution process	6.7	40	26.7	18.7	8	3.42	1.206
Stakeholders have the necessary skills and knowledge to participate effectively in land conflict resolution	8	5.3	26	27.3	33.3	2.18	0.854
Aggregate	3.721	1.031

Table 1 indicate that the statement "Community members are frequently involved in land conflict resolution meetings" has a high mean of 4.17 and a low standard deviation of 0.565, indicating that respondents strongly agree that community members are regularly involved in such meetings. The low variability suggests consistent perceptions across the board, highlighting the importance of grassroots participation in conflict resolution processes. This strong involvement helps build trust and a sense of ownership among community members, making it more likely for resolutions to be accepted and maintained. Regarding the statement "A diverse range of stakeholders participate in decision-making processes for land conflicts," the mean of 3.8 shows moderate agreement, but the higher standard deviation of 1.133 indicates mixed perceptions. While diversity in stakeholder participation is acknowledged, the variability suggests that some stakeholders may feel excluded or underrepresented in decision-making. This implies that while efforts to involve a broad range of participants exist, there is still room for improvement to ensure that all relevant

groups consistently have a voice in these processes. The statement "The decision-making process is inclusive of all relevant stakeholders" has a mean of 3.88 and a standard deviation of 1.073, reflecting general agreement with some variation. This suggests that, overall, respondents feel that the decision-making process is inclusive, though not universal. This inconsistency points to the need for better efforts in consistently ensuring that all relevant stakeholders are included in discussions, which would promote fairness and more widely accepted outcomes in land conflict resolutions. For the statement "Information regarding land conflict resolution processes is easily accessible," the high mean of 4.23 indicates strong agreement, though the standard deviation of 1.141 reveals some variation. This suggests that while many respondents find information easily accessible, some may still face challenges. Enhancing access to information, particularly for marginalized or remote stakeholders, could improve transparency and engagement in the resolution process.

"Updates on the progress of land conflict resolutions are provided regularly" received a mean of 3.87, reflecting moderate agreement, but the high standard deviation of 1.169 suggests differing experiences. While some stakeholders receive regular updates, others may not. Ensuring consistent and timely updates for all stakeholders would improve transparency and help build trust in the resolution process, leading to higher satisfaction and better conflict management. The statement "The information shared during conflict resolution is transparent" has a mean of 3.9, indicating general agreement among respondents, though the standard deviation of 1.026 shows some variability in perceptions. This implies that while transparency is generally upheld, there is room for improvement in consistently delivering transparent information across all land conflict resolution processes. Enhancing transparency would increase stakeholder confidence and promote more equitable outcomes. On the statement "Training programs for stakeholders involved in land conflict resolution are effective," the mean of 3.46 and a standard deviation of 1.115 suggest a neutral to slightly positive view of the effectiveness of training programs, with considerable variation. This indicates that while some stakeholders find the training beneficial, others do not. To improve engagement, training programs could be made more tailored to the specific needs of participants, ensuring that all stakeholders are adequately prepared for their roles in the conflict resolution process. The statement "Capacity-building initiatives enhance stakeholders' participation in the resolution process" has a mean of 3.42, showing a neutral stance, with a standard deviation of 1.206 indicating significant variability in responses. This suggests that while capacity-building efforts exist, their impact on improving participation is inconsistent. Strengthening these initiatives to ensure that they are effectively enhancing the skills and involvement of all stakeholders would lead to

more meaningful contributions to the conflict resolution process.

Finally, the statement "Stakeholders have the necessary skills and knowledge to participate effectively in land conflict resolution" has a low mean of 2.18, indicating general disagreement, with a standard deviation of 0.854. This shows that most respondents feel that stakeholders lack the skills and knowledge required for effective participation. Addressing this significant gap through comprehensive training and capacity-building programs is crucial for improving the overall effectiveness of the land conflict resolution process. The overall aggregate mean of 3.721 indicates that respondents generally agree with the statements regarding stakeholder engagement and conflict resolution processes. However, the aggregate standard deviation of 1.031 shows notable variability, suggesting room for improvement in areas such as capacity-building, inclusivity, and transparency. Addressing these areas could enhance the overall effectiveness of stakeholder engagement and the resolution of land conflicts in Kenya's ASAL counties.

Land Conflict Resolution

The Likert scale was employed to gauge respondents' perceptions of the statement, with options ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree), enabling participants to express their degree of agreement or disagreement with the statement. In order to guide analysis and interpretation purposes, a mean close to 1 indicates strong disagreement with the statement; a mean close to 3 suggests neutrality or ambivalence; and a mean close to 5 indicates strong agreement with the statement. Moreover, based on the standard deviations ranging from approximately 1.0 or lower may indicate a relatively high level of agreement or consensus among respondents (lower variability). Standard deviations exceeding 1.0 or higher suggest greater diversity or disagreement among respondents (higher variability).

Table 2. Land Conflict Resolution

Statement	SA (%)	A (%)	N (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean	Std. Dev
There has been a noticeable reduction in the frequency of land conflicts over the past year	16.7	16.7	11.3	53.3	2	3.03	0.549
The number of land conflicts recorded this year has decreased compared to previous years.	1.3	4	25.3	53.3	16	2.86	1.124
Conflict reduction efforts are effective	22	23.3	16.7	20	18	3.11	1.426
I am satisfied with the fairness of the land conflict resolution process	16	18	20	22.7	23.3	3.05	1.353
The resolution process is transparent and inclusive	20.7	19.3	16.7	26	17.3	3.00	1.409
The resolutions agreed upon during the conflict resolution process have been fully implemented	19.3	38.7	13.3	24	4.7	3.48	1.108
There are no significant challenges hindering the implementation of conflict resolution agreements	16.7	18	14.7	28.7	22	2.79	1.407
The implementation of resolutions has been timely and effective	15.3	16	18	27.3	23.3	2.73	1.385
The conflict resolution outcomes have been fair to all parties involved	19.3	16.7	20.7	20	23.3	2.89	1.44
The needs and concerns of marginalized groups have been adequately addressed in the resolution process.	24.7	18	20.7	18.7	18	3.13	1.439
The resolution outcomes are perceived as equitable by all stakeholders	18	22	20.7	14.7	24.7	2.94	1.443
Aggregate	3.02	1.272

Table 2 shows that the statement "There has been a noticeable reduction in the frequency of land conflicts over the past year" shows a mean of 3.03, indicating a neutral perception, with a low standard deviation of 0.549, suggesting relative consensus. This implies that respondents generally do not feel there has been a significant reduction in land conflicts over the past year. The findings indicate that conflict resolution efforts may not be producing the desired impact in terms of reducing the frequency of conflicts, highlighting the need for more effective interventions. The statement "The number of land conflicts recorded this year has decreased compared to previous years" has a mean of 2.86, suggesting disagreement, and a high standard deviation of 1.124, showing variation in opinions. This indicates that many respondents believe there has not been a meaningful decrease in land conflicts, with some possibly perceiving an increase. The high variability in responses may reflect differing local experiences, but

overall, this suggests that current strategies for reducing land conflicts have not been sufficiently effective.

In response to the statement "Conflict reduction efforts are effective," the mean score of 3.11 reflects a neutral stance, while the high standard deviation of 1.426 points to significant variation in views. This indicates that respondents are divided on the effectiveness of conflict reduction efforts, with some believing these efforts are working, while others remain unconvinced. The high variability suggests the need for more consistent and impactful conflict reduction strategies across different areas to build stakeholder confidence in their effectiveness. The statement "I am satisfied with the fairness of the land conflict resolution process" has a mean of 3.05, reflecting a neutral response, with a standard deviation of 1.353 showing substantial variation. This indicates mixed feelings about the fairness of the process, with some respondents feeling satisfied while

others do not. The high variation implies that there may be inconsistencies in how fairness is perceived across different cases or regions, suggesting that improving the fairness and transparency of the process could enhance stakeholder trust and satisfaction.

For the statement "The resolution process is transparent and inclusive," the mean of 3.00 suggests neutrality, with the high standard deviation of 1.409 indicating a wide range of opinions. Some respondents may feel that the process is transparent and inclusive, while others do not share this view. This inconsistency points to a need for greater efforts to ensure that transparency and inclusiveness are applied uniformly in all land conflict resolution cases, ensuring that all stakeholders feel adequately involved and informed. The statement "The resolutions agreed upon during the conflict resolution process have been fully implemented" has a mean of 3.48, showing slight agreement, and a standard deviation of 1.108, indicating some variation. This suggests that while some resolutions are implemented effectively, others may face delays or obstacles. Improving the consistency of implementation would likely enhance the overall effectiveness of land conflict resolution and increase stakeholders' confidence in the process.

"There are no significant challenges hindering the implementation of conflict resolution agreements" has a mean of 2.79, indicating disagreement, with a high standard deviation of 1.407, reflecting varied perceptions. This suggests that most respondents believe there are significant challenges to implementing conflict resolution agreements, and the variability indicates that these challenges may be more prominent in some areas than others. Addressing these challenges is crucial to improving the overall success of land conflict resolution efforts. The statement "The implementation of resolutions has been timely and effective" has a mean of 2.73, showing general disagreement, with a standard deviation of 1.385 indicating diverse views. This suggests that many respondents feel that the implementation of resolutions has not been timely or effective. The variability in responses

implies that while some cases may be implemented efficiently, others experience significant delays or inefficiencies, highlighting the need for improvements in the execution phase of the conflict resolution process.

In response to the statement "The conflict resolution outcomes have been fair to all parties involved," the mean of 2.89 reflects disagreement, with a high standard deviation of 1.44 indicating variability. This suggests that many stakeholders do not feel that the outcomes have been fair to all parties, though some may have different experiences. The perception of fairness is crucial to the success of conflict resolution, and these findings imply that more effort is needed to ensure that outcomes are equitable and just for all involved. "The needs and concerns of marginalized groups have been adequately addressed in the resolution process" received a mean of 3.13, indicating slight agreement, but the high standard deviation of 1.439 shows considerable variation. While some respondents feel that the needs of marginalized groups are being addressed, others believe there is more work to be done. This suggests that conflict resolution processes may not be consistently inclusive of marginalized groups, and additional attention should be given to ensuring their concerns are fully considered.

Lastly, the statement "The resolution outcomes are perceived as equitable by all stakeholders" has a mean of 2.94, reflecting disagreement, with a standard deviation of 1.443 showing significant variation. This indicates that most respondents do not perceive the outcomes as equitable, though there are differences in opinion. Ensuring equitable outcomes for all stakeholders is essential for the long-term success of land conflict resolution efforts, and these findings suggest that greater focus on fairness and inclusivity is needed. Aggregate Analysis: The overall aggregate mean of 3.02 suggests that respondents have neutral to slightly negative perceptions of the land conflict resolution process. The high aggregate standard deviation of 1.272 indicates significant variability in responses, reflecting mixed experiences and perceptions. This variability suggests that while some aspects of the process may work well in

certain areas, there are significant challenges related to fairness, transparency, inclusivity, and implementation that need to be addressed to improve the overall effectiveness of land conflict resolution efforts in Kenya's ASAL counties.

Hypothesis Testing

Based on the results of the Pearson correlation analysis in Table 3 shown below a strong positive relationship between stakeholder engagement and land conflict resolution, with a correlation coefficient of 0.641. This indicates that higher levels of stakeholder participation, transparency in information, and capacity-building efforts are closely associated with better outcomes in land

conflict resolution. The statistical significance of the correlation ($p = 0.000$) highlights that this relationship is unlikely to have occurred by chance, suggesting that stakeholder engagement is a critical factor in resolving land conflicts effectively. This finding is significant for conflict-prone areas like Kenya's ASAL counties, where inclusive participation is key to reducing disputes over land. Therefore, confidently the null hypothesis is rejected, emphasizing that stakeholder engagement is crucial for reducing land disputes, particularly in conflict-prone areas like Kenya's ASAL counties.

Table 3. Correlation Matrix for Independent and Dependent Variables

		Stakeholder Engagement	Land Conflict Resolution
Stakeholder Engagement	Pearson Correlation	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.001	
	N	195	
Land Conflict Resolution	Pearson Correlation	0.641	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	195	

Discussion

The implication of these findings is that stakeholder engagement should be prioritized in land conflict resolution processes. Stakeholders who are involved in the process, have access to transparent information, and possess the necessary skills and knowledge, are more likely to contribute positively to resolving conflicts. The correlation suggests that when communities, local authorities, and other relevant parties work together and are informed, they are better equipped to arrive at sustainable and equitable resolutions. This is consistent with existing literature, such as the work of Ogola and Onyango (2018), which emphasizes that transparent and participatory processes build trust among stakeholders and reduce the recurrence of land conflicts. Additionally, the strong correlation aligns with collaborative governance theory, which stresses the importance of multi-stakeholder participation in resolving complex issues like land disputes. As

shown by Mutunga et al. (2020) and Ndegwa and Owuor (2019), involving a broad range of stakeholders leads to more durable and equitable outcomes. These findings suggest that improving stakeholder engagement through capacity-building programs, transparent information sharing, and inclusive decision-making platforms could significantly enhance the effectiveness of land conflict resolution processes in Kenya's ASAL regions. The study underscores the need for policies that foster greater stakeholder involvement as a means of addressing the persistent challenge of land conflict.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, the strong positive and significant correlation between stakeholder engagement and land conflict resolution underscores the critical role that inclusive participation plays in effectively addressing land disputes. The

findings indicate that enhancing stakeholder involvement through transparent communication, capacity-building initiatives, and collaborative decision-making can lead to more successful and equitable resolutions. As such, policymakers and practitioners should prioritize strategies that promote active stakeholder engagement to foster sustainable conflict resolution in Kenya's ASAL counties and similar contexts, ultimately contributing to greater stability and harmony in land management practices. Therefore, to enhance stakeholder engagement in land conflict resolution, it is recommended that policymakers establish multi-stakeholder platforms to facilitate regular dialogue among diverse groups, ensuring that marginalized voices are included in decision-making. Additionally, capacity-building initiatives should be implemented to equip stakeholders with essential skills in negotiation and understanding land rights, empowering them to participate more effectively. Promoting transparency in the resolution process is crucial, as providing accessible and clear information will build trust and foster cooperation among stakeholders. Finally, incorporating feedback mechanisms will allow stakeholders to express their concerns and experiences, ensuring that the resolution process is responsive to their needs. By adopting these strategies, stakeholders can collaboratively address land conflicts, leading to more equitable and sustainable land conflict resolution outcomes in Kenya's ASAL counties and similar regions.

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